

Multi-task learning for forward prediction of dispersion diagrams in 2D acoustic metamaterials

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Abstract—Metamaterials are unique solid structures which can cease the transmission of waves within a specified frequency range. They have widespread application in critical fields like ultrasound imaging, wearable health devices and others. The topological design of metamaterials is a computationally demanding process and often requires human supervision of domain experts. In this paper we present a deep learning based computer vision architecture to predict the dispersion relation vectors from metamaterial topology images, referred as forward prediction problem. The novel contribution of our work is a methodology to use multi-task learning along with transfer learning for forward modeling. We propose to use pretrained vision models with multiple heads, one for each of the dispersion branches. We demonstrate through experimental results that it is possible to train such a network and do so efficiently.

Index Terms—Multi-task learning, Transfer learning, metamaterials, phononic crystals

I. INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials are artificially designed materials having properties not commonly found in nature. They have wide range of application in medical research including medical imaging [1], therapeutic devices [2], biomedical sensors [2], orthopedic implants [3] and others. They are classified into sub types based on the waves they interact with. For example optical metamaterials interact with electromagnetic waves and acoustic metamaterials are designed to manipulate acoustic waves. In this work we are primarily interested in topological design of acoustic metamaterials.

Acoustic metamaterials (AM), also referred to as phononic crystals (PnC) can be designed to prevent the transmission of ultrasonic waves of specific frequencies. The frequency range within which the ultrasonic waves cannot pass through such crystals are called bandgaps. The width and location of bandgap within the full frequency range of dispersion relation is a subject of desire for research and development. Traditionally the topology of PnC is designed by domain experts with structural intuition. Correspondingly the bandgap is calculated using numerical methods representative of the

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physical property of structures. The traditional method of calculating dispersion relation is computationally intensive which makes it difficult to explore multiple topology design spaces.

In the past decade as the use of acoustic metamaterials have increased, various types of computational methods have been proposed to design and build PnC. In [4], the authors presented a mechanism to design 2D phononic crystals to maximize band gap frequency range while minimizing midpoint frequency. They use Genetic algorithm (GA) for maximizing the possibility of finding a unit cell with maximum bandgap.

Jiang et al. [5] used convolutional neural network (CNN) to learn the mapping between a given image pixel matrix representing structural topology and the resulting dispersion relation matrix of PnC. They consider 2D PnC with pAm plane symmetry geometry and generate binary images of structures with morphological image processing. Dispersion relation comprising the first 10 eigenfrequencies for wave vector are computed using traditional finite element method (FEM) and normalized with transverse wave velocity. They train a separate neural network for each of the 10 eigenfrequency vector and learn the mapping between structural topology and dispersion relation.

In [6] the authors propose a semi-analytical method called periodic spectral finite element (TP-SFE) to numerically compute the dispersion relation of a given PnC structure. They trained a CNN model with few layers of convolutions and finally a linear operation to predict the dispersion matrix for each input topology image. Similar to [5] they too trained a separate CNN for each of the first 10 band structures of elastic waves.

Building on the previous works we propose the following to compute dispersion relation as a part of forward modeling:

- use transfer learning to learn preliminary features from structural topology images of acoustic metamaterials
- apply a multi-task neural network framework to learn unique representation for each of the 10 eigenfrequency vectors in dispersion diagram

In section II we explain our method and motivation for deep learning choices. In section III we present our experimental setup and show how we train the proposed neural network architecture. In the next section IV, we present experimental

results. Finally we share our concluding remarks in section V with some future works.

II. METHODS

A. Problem Setup and Dataset

The objective of forward modeling is to use metamaterial topology image as input and train a model which can predict dispersion relation consisting of eigenfrequency matrix. We use open source data provided by Jiang et al. [5] to train deep learning models and experimental validation. The dataset consist of samples in two groups, each with 70796 and 87474 observations respectively. Each sample in the former group has metamaterial topologies with bandgap, while the latter group have topologies with and without bandgap. Since we are only interested in the forward modeling of eigenfrequencies, we consider the second group with 87474 samples for our experiments. Each sample consist of one binary metamaterial topology image and one dispersion relation matrix. The images were generated using morphological image processing and optimized with post-processing to satisfy manufacturing constraints and porosity requirements.

This gives us a labeled dataset \mathcal{D} of M samples where $\mathcal{D}_i = \{x_i, y_i\}; i = 1, \dots, M$; x_i is a binary image of size $(50 \times 50 \times 1)$ and y_i is a dispersion relation vector of size (10×31) . Using \mathcal{D} we want to find a function $f(\cdot)$, such that $\hat{y}_i = \arg \min_f J(f(x), y)$, where \hat{y} is the prediction output from function $f(\cdot)$ and J is a loss function. We divide the dataset into three groups having 80%, 10% and 10% of data as train set, validation set and test set respectively.

B. Transfer Learning

While building a machine learning model we often assume the train, validation and test data come from the same data distribution. However, in real world scenarios this assumption may not hold true. Additionally, training a separate model for each new data distribution comes with a computational cost. Because of these reasons transfer learning is a well accepted practice in machine learning. It is implemented by learning representation from a *source domain* and used on a *target domain*. We have publicly available models with large and small parameter size. While the former group of models serve high accuracy requirements, the latter group is used for low memory and inference time requirements in model deployment. Fig. 1 shows a pictorial representation of the transfer learning process. It starts with training a base model on large number of publicly available images and than fine tuning the final layer often referred to as *head* or multiple layers of the base model on a newer dataset.

In this work we are considering four different types of base model architecture as a part of transfer learning, EfficientNetB0 [7], ResNet50 [8], Inception net [9] and MobileNetV3 [10]. Each of these models have an unique architectural novelty of pre-training. ResNet uses skip connections and batch normalization to train deeper networks and deal with vanishing gradient problem. Inception models uses an innovative *inception modules*, which are essentially smaller network structures

Fig. 1. Transfer learning in computer vision

inside a larger network along with factorized convolutions. MobileNet uses an inverted bottleneck structure to reduce computational cost while maintaining accuracy. While EfficientNet uses a depth wise separable convolutions to reduce parameter size while maintaining high accuracy using an swish activation. All base models used were pre-trained on ImageNet dataset [11].

C. Multi-Task Learning

A classical deep learning model consist of an input layer, some middle layers and an output layer. Based on output values a suitable loss is computed through a loss function which is then used to update network weights by computing gradients with respect to loss. For example in object detection a network might output a vector of real values, each one representing probability of an object being present in the given image. Here, the network is doing a single task of whether objects are present in an image. In multi-task learning a network is trained to do more than one task simultaneously or learn different data distribution of a common problem. For example in [12] Zhang et al., propose a mechanism to jointly learn facial landmark detection along with head pose estimation and facial attribute inference through a deep learning model. In multi-task learning parameters are simultaneously learned through a shared model. In practice this is implemented either as *hard parameter sharing* or *soft parameter sharing*. In the former case the model weights are jointly learned by minimizing more than one loss function, however for the latter case the weights are independently learned through a joint objective function. This has several benefits including reduction in training cycles, constricted overfitting, shared representation and increased data usability. Among these, the speedup of learning for related downstream tasks is the most critical benefit. However, this process is not trivial and introduces several challenges like learning joint distribution of datasets and taking into account problems with opposing needs.

We present our multi-task learning framework in Fig. 2. We use a base model as a part of transfer learning explained in section (II-B) to get rich features for input images. As a final layer of the base model, we use a collection of 10 dense networks to predict each of the eigenfrequency vector in the

TABLE I
STAGE I - VALIDATION MAE

	out_0	out_1	out_2	out_3	out_4	out_5	out_6	out_7	out_8	out_9	mean
ResNet50V2	0.050	0.051	0.066	0.106	0.106	0.101	0.112	0.109	0.109	0.114	0.092
InceptionV3	0.056	0.056	0.080	0.113	0.115	0.116	0.129	0.120	0.127	0.130	0.104
MobileNetV2	0.047	0.052	0.071	0.092	0.094	0.095	0.105	0.102	0.107	0.115	0.088
EfficientNetB0	0.084	0.082	0.107	0.142	0.145	0.159	0.169	0.163	0.168	0.166	0.138
mean	0.059	0.06	0.081	0.113	0.115	0.118	0.129	0.124	0.128	0.131	
standard-deviation	0.017	0.015	0.018	0.021	0.022	0.029	0.029	0.027	0.028	0.024	

TABLE II
STAGE II - VALIDATION MAE

	out_0	out_1	out_2	out_3	out_4	out_5	out_6	out_7	out_8	out_9	mean
ResNet50V2	0.022	0.022	0.032	0.041	0.044	0.051	0.060	0.060	0.063	0.071	0.047
InceptionV3	0.037	0.041	0.058	0.079	0.084	0.094	0.110	0.108	0.114	0.121	0.085
MobileNetV2	0.023	0.025	0.038	0.048	0.051	0.058	0.068	0.068	0.071	0.080	0.053
EfficientNetB0	0.088	0.083	0.106	0.159	0.164	0.180	0.176	0.173	0.178	0.168	0.148
mean	0.042	0.043	0.059	0.082	0.086	0.096	0.103	0.102	0.106	0.11	
standard-deviation	0.031	0.028	0.034	0.054	0.055	0.059	0.053	0.052	0.052	0.045	

dispersion relation. In previous work [5], the 10 branches of a dispersion vector are considered to be from different data distribution and hence they propose to train identical but completely separate neural network models for each of the dispersion branch. In our work, by framing the problem as multi-task learning, we reduce computational cost by training just one neural network model with 10 heads, one for each dispersion branch data distribution.

Fig. 2. Multi-task learning

III. EXPERIMENTS

The input of pre-trained models are RGB images with standardized dimension. Since the metamaterial topology images [5] are binary images, we up sample the input images from resolution $(50 \times 50 \times 1)$ to $(224 \times 224 \times 3)$. Image resizing is a conventional part of computer vision [13] for suitable task. An alternative of this is to have a learnable layer within the pre-trained model, which will be considered in our future work. Here we up-sample the images using bilinear interpolation available in TensorFlow which computes new images based on the weighted pixel value by distances. Four separate base models from the TensorFlow library are used to extract representation features as a part of transfer learning namely ResNet50V2, InceptionV3, MobileNetV2 and EfficientNetB0. We specify the head for each of these models to be 10 different (31×1) dense vectors. So each model takes an input image of $(224 \times 224 \times 3)$ and outputs 10 separate vectors of size (31×1) .

Our networks is trained with a batch size of 128 samples using *Adam* optimizer. The reason for choosing a larger batch size is to have a smoother learning curve. However, with smaller batch sizes a certain amount of noise is added to the learning process which may help in generalization. Considering a train set size of approximately 70000 samples, available memory resources and choice of learning rate a batch size of 128 samples is a good balance between generalization and convergence. In our experience we did not notice and over fitting which can be attributed to the batch size. We use two stage training process for our models, referred as *stage I* and *stage II* in the rest of the paper.

- **stage I**, In this stage, we freeze all layers of the pretrained models except last layer (head) and train it for 6 epochs. A learning rate of $1e - 2$ is used for training during this stage.
- **stage II**, In the second stage, we unfreeze at most the last 20 layers in each network and update their weights with a learning rate of $1e - 5$. The choice was made considering available computational resources and time as a heuristic.

Mean absolute error (MAE) is used as a loss function to be minimized by the network. The computing infrastructure on which these experiments were performed consist of 8 core Intel i7-9700KF CPU with 8GB NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 GPU and 32 GB of RAM.

IV. RESULTS

Table I presents the MAE scores on validation dataset after 6 epochs of training the model head, with all other layers frozen. The lowest value from each of the 10 dispersion relation vectors (out_0 to out_9) is marked in bold. We see that ResNet50V2 and MobileNetV2 doing better than others with MobileNetV2 being the best in 7 out of 10 output vector. We need to be cautious from assuming too much from the results here however the results does indicate the inherent representation abilities of these models trained on ImageNet data.

Fig. 3. MAE scores across epochs. (A) Stage I MAE score on train dataset. (B) Stage I MAE score on validation dataset (C) Stage II MAE score on train dataset (D) Stage II MAE score on validation dataset

Fig. 4. (A0, A1) Example Metamaterial structure (B0, B1) True dispersion relation values (C0, C1) Predicted dispersion relation values

TABLE III
STAGE II - TEST MAE

	out_0	out_1	out_2	out_3	out_4	out_5	out_6	out_7	out_8	out_9	mean
ResNet50V2	0.022	0.041	0.051	0.060	0.072	0.022	0.041	0.051	0.060	0.072	0.049
InceptionV3	0.041	0.079	0.094	0.107	0.121	0.041	0.079	0.094	0.107	0.121	0.088
MobileNetV2	0.026	0.048	0.058	0.068	0.081	0.026	0.048	0.058	0.068	0.081	0.056
EfficientNetB0	0.082	0.156	0.177	0.171	0.168	0.082	0.156	0.177	0.171	0.168	0.151
mean	0.043	0.081	0.095	0.102	0.111	0.043	0.081	0.095	0.102	0.111	
standard-deviation	0.028	0.053	0.058	0.051	0.044	0.028	0.053	0.058	0.051	0.044	

In Table II we present the validation MAE scores of model training from stage II where at most the last 20 layers were unfroze and trained for 21 epochs. Here the lowest MAE is recorded by ResNet50V2 in all 10 of the dispersion relation vectors (out_0 to out_9). We mark the lowest value for each columns in bold. Among the 10 outputs in ResNet50V2, we see MAE values in the range of 0.02 to 0.07, where the model is doing relatively better on some branches than others. One can also see that MobileNetV2 is a close second in MAE score for many of the output branches. At this point we decide that we want to limit out computation expenditure with at least one clear leader among the models.

Next we consider the model with lowest MAE from Table II and plot it across epochs. These figures also include the metric values for all 10 different dispersion relation frequencies for analysis. Fig. 3 (A) and (B) shows the MAE score on train and validation dataset, respectively during stage I across 6 epochs. From Fig. 3 (A) we can observe that the error line plateaus after 1 epoch, which implies that there was very little learning happening after this point. This is a good consideration for fine tuning a model head and limiting computational resource. In Fig. 3 (C) and (D) we present the MAE score from stage II on train and validation dataset, respectively. Here there is a gradual decline of error across epochs. Interestingly the MAE values do not plateau but stays very close to zero (0.02 to 0.07) and (0.02 to 0.07) for train and validation, respectively.

Table III presents the MAE scores on test dataset of our trained models from STAGE II. As seen earlier with validation dataset results (Table II), here also ResNet50V2 has the lowest MAE score among the four model families. One reason for ResNet50V2 doing better than other models is its abilities to learn rich features representation across its 50 layers aided by residual blocks and skip connections. In comparison MobileNetV2 and EfficientNetB0 are relatively smaller models and considered for low computation requirement tasks. The fact that MobileNetV2 has very close MAE score in comparison to ResNet50V2 is a positive indication form engineering and deployment perspective.

Even though our models were trained with MAE loss, we recorded a mean relative error (MRE) of 10.87 on held out test set. Our understanding is that, adapting the head for each output branch and training for longer epochs can reduce MRE value further. In Fig. 4, we show two metamaterial topology design structures (A0 and A1) with their original dispersion relation vector (B0 and B1) and predicted dispersion relation vector (C0 and C1) respectively. Fig. 4-C0 has a MAE value

of 0.01 and MRE value of 2.3. Where as Fig. 4-C1 has a MAE value of 0.01 and MRE value of 2.43.

V. CONCLUSION

Our results are encouraging to consider new research in topology optimization of metamaterials. The benefit of pre-trained models aided with lightweight multi-task learning framework is clearly seen. In future, we want to consider different architecture for each of the output head in predicting dispersion relation. Another encouraging result is the low MAE values of MobileNetV2, only second to ResNet50V2 in Table III. This open up possibilities in using light weight architectures for problems similar to ours.

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